

Module:

BB-4312 Organizational Development and Change

Title:

Multiple Case Analysis

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Executive Summary

This assignment aims to investigate the possible solutions to the multiple case analysis by suggesting new strategies to the three organizations. The organizations for this multiple case analysis are BruTEL, Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT) and Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV). These case studies are analyzed with the help of using conceptual models in order to observe the facts and issues of the three case studies. The possible solutions are also supported with literature reviews of previous studies that were previously been done in other countries and that it is possible to be applied in Brunei context. Included in this section is also the pros and cons of implementing the proposed solutions. After analyzing the three case studies, several recommendations have been decided and finalized in order to solve the issues that the organization encountered.

The following recommendations have been made:

- Provide the training necessary for the elderlies in regard of the “Go Paperless” initiative as proposed by BruTEL.
- Improved the management of Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV) in terms of giving it exposure and adding more activities that attract visitors from internal and international.
- Collaborated with the relevant public and private agencies in order to get sponsorship for SCOT future projects.

1.0 Problem Statement

1.1 BruTEL's 'Going Paperless' Initiative

BruTel Cellular is a telecommunication company based in Brunei since the year 2014 (Musa & Idris, 2018). In order to fulfill the nation's vision of 2035, BruTel incorporated its initiative on Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the beginning of 2017. The 2035 vision has the objectives of seeing the growth of people with skilled that have the standard of international recognition, the growth of the living standard in order to create a more active and sustainable economic expansion. Hence, by referring to the 2035 vision, BruTEL has come up with its CSR under the foundation of four Areas. These areas include Arts & Culture, Education, Entrepreneurship, and Environment.

In line with the environment area, BruTEL's Communications and Media Manager, Jamilah Kassim decided to consider with the initiative of going green in order to improve their obligation and what they offer to the people. Nonetheless, Jamilah Kassim knew that this is rather a challenging initiative to be done. The green initiatives of BruTEL include the idea of changing the way they work that is by going "paperless". This is an attempt to decrease the carbon emission and depletion of materials that are valuable. This is due to the fact that Brunei is the highest country with the most waste produced (Hayat, 2017). Therefore, by implementing this green initiative, it is hope to lessen the excessive wastage that occurred when printing paper and at the same time, reducing the number of trees that are cut down to create papers (Odell, 2008).

Although by going "paperless" can help the environment condition, the idea does not seem to suit elderly customers who are not following the modern technology advancement. These elderlies have a hard time to navigate and manage their account without having someone to assist them. According to Kazimi (2014), making use of technology can be complicated and thus, these elderlies feel hesitant to join in the latest platforms. As a result, this might possibly affect BruTEL in terms of losing a segment of potential customers as well as present customers. BruTEL's Communications and Media Manager, Jamilah stated that these senior citizen much prefer the traditional method to send out billing system rather than having to access the bills online. The reason why they prefer the older method is because the paper bills act as a reminder to pay their bills monthly. Without the paper bills, there are concerned that they will forgot to pay the bills.

Another issue why some customers do not like the idea of going green is because of the issue linked to customers' password fatigue. This is when the customers regardless of their age are tasked because of having countless different passwords of different platforms to remember. Furthermore, admission to this initiative are considered as a burdensome process.

1.2 Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV)

Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV) is a social enterprise business on which the objectives are to conserve the surroundings while in return, provides economic opportunities. It is a type of business involving the local community such as the Iban tribe. SEV is owned by Leslie Chiang on which he designed the concept of SEV and organize funding, planned and the whole project. Several initiatives have been made to conserve the environment such as the plantation of organic farm, not allowing pesticides to be used in farms area, less used of electric utility and the Iban tribe uses the collection of rain water. They also encourage the concept of 3R (Reduce,

Reuse and Recycle). Plastics waste are to be delivered to government bins and biodegradables are properly buried. They do not encourage the use of plastic in the area and the recycle bins there are handmade. This proves that they do take this matter seriously in attempt to conserve the forest natural habitat.

As attempts were made to preserve the forest as well as making this ecotourism business a success, Leslie Chiang encountered some issues. In the beginning, Leslie used goods and materials that are ecosystem friendly, however, it became eroded over time and had to be fixed many times. The owner then decided to just combine the concept with modern design and materials as to not waste cost on maintaining the original natural materials. Another issue that they faced is due to the Brunei weather. Due to the humid weather, it damages the infrastructure and the wind quickly erodes the materials. Such innovations does not seem to appeal to the weather here. Furthermore, Leslie Chiang have difficulties in getting regular electricity, and portable water supply.

Ecotourism business is considered a new type of tourism business and hence, there are shortage of skilled workers that play an important role in doing green businesses and to achieve SEV objectives. SEV also encountered competition from countries such as Sarawak and Miri whereby not only these retreats have more local but also expatriates that support their retreat. Therefore, more opportunities for them as they have a lot more to offer and attract tourists to visit. As of SEV, more accommodations are in need as there are only less than 10 beds are available at the moment. Without proper and thorough planning, the integrity of ecosystem and local people have the potential to be threaten. This is due to the rise in visitors coming in to environment that are prone to degrade. Similarly, local people that have been living there for so long can be intimidated by foreign visitors as well as their wealth.

1.3 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project

Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT) is a register Non-government Organization (NGO) that has a role of carrying out corporate social responsibilities (CSRs). The main objective for the establishment of SCOT is to lessen the number of poverty in this country. There are assumptions that NGOs work voluntarily and funding is not needed, which is totally wrong. Government funding are very much needed by NGOs in Brunei for the purpose of project-based activities. SCOT is not an exception to this matter. The "Green Xchange" project is created by SCOT with the purpose of educating the people on the advantages of exchanging recyclable materials with basic necessities like rice. This program become the major event that was held annually. Upon implementing the Green Xchange program, SCOT has faced some challenges like uncertainty over food prices and the possible lower rates for the recyclable materials. In this case, SCOT need to find other option other than rice to be exchanged with the recyclables such as locally grown vegetables and fruits produce.

In order to sustain in the market, SCOT relies from the public by getting donations and sponsorships to get through. The uncertainty in this financial matter makes it hard to perform better and improve the CSR projects that are created. Therefore, it is vital for NGOs such as SCOT to have variety fund sources rather than depending on donations and respective organizations to sponsor. In addition to this issue, SCOT finds it hard to get funds from abroad organizations or governments since other countries may also have their own clauses and hence, can cause conflict. Although SCOT received sponsorships, it is usually non-monetary support such as free space in a facility and technical support. Monetary aids are rather hard to receive and it is considered a challenging mission.

2.0 Case Analysis

2.1 BruTEL's 'Going Paperless' Initiative

Positive Model

In order to solve the issues faced by BruTEL, the positive model of planned change will be used in analyzing this case. There are five phases under this model.

1. Initiate the Inquiry

- The change of process in billing payment from the physical transaction to online method that is through e-billing. The senior citizens might be difficult to adapt to this change as they are so used to paying their bills the traditional way. They are also not as techno-savvy and need assistance to help them. Another issue why some customers do not like the idea of going green is because of the issue linked to customers' password fatigue. This is when the customers regardless of their age are tasked because of having countless different passwords of different platforms to remember. This can overwhelmed some individuals.

2. Inquire into Best Practices

- Although transforming to electronic bills can be quite a challenge, it actually has many advantages and benefits if it is being planned, organized and execute properly. The customers of BruTEL needs to be informed early on the reasons why the company proposed this initiative. This can be done by letting them know about the goals that are in line with the nation's vision 2035 that BruTEL is trying to achieve and participate in achieving the vision.

3. Discover the Themes

- For this case, the theme will be a green transformation that is in line with Brunei's vision of 2035 that stated that the objective of seeing the growth of people with skilled that have the standard of international recognition, the growth of the living standard in order to create a more active and sustainable economic expansion. Based on the 2035's vision, BruTEL has come up with this green project as a way to achieve their goal in preserving the natural environment of Brunei.

4. Envision a Preferred Future

- Through this green project, BruTEL has proposed with the 'Go Paperless' Initiative which is a way to reduce carbon emission and wastage of materials. By going with the concept of paperless, it is hope to lessen the excess waste in order to cut cost on paper and printing. This action will also protect the trees from being cut down to produce paper (Odell, 2008). According to The World Counts (2020), producing paper cause environmental problems such as deforestation, wastage issue, excessive use amounts of energy and it also contributes to water and air pollution. Therefore, by eliminating the usage of papers in the company, BruTel hopes to be an organization that help to deliver the initiative in line with the Vision 2035.

5. Design and Deliver Ways to Create the Future

- Although it might be a challenge for BruTel to totally eliminate the usage of paper, it can be implemented if it is being done stage by stage. The customers should also be informed and educated on why this transformation is actually a good thing to implement. This can be made

by making awareness on the danger of producing paper that can harm the environment and by letting them why online transaction is the best option them.

2.2 Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV)

In order to solve the issues faced by SEV, the Kotter's Eight Steps Model will be used in analyzing this case. There are eight steps under this model.

1. Establish a sense of urgency for change

- Brunei has been completely dependent on oil exports for so long and this is not good for the country's economy. This is why it is important to develop a more diverse economy. Although eco-tourism is still considered new in Brunei, it is a good effort to begin with since Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV) has the potential to grow with proper planning, changes and improvement. Through proper management, SEV can be the top of tourist attraction in Brunei.

2. Create guiding condition

- This is the step where Leslie Chiang, the owner of SEV, needs to sit down and discuss with the relevant authorities such as the Ministry of Primary Resources and Tourism and Radio Television Brunei (RTB). SEV lacks of exposure to people whether it is people from inside the country or outside of Brunei. As the owner, Leslie needs to discuss on how to increase the awareness of the SEV as well as promoting it with the relevant departments. Besides from that, the owner also needs to discuss on how to improve the facilities at SEV with the Department of Electric Services and Public Works Department. As mentioned previously, the SEV experienced irregular electricity and lack of portable supply of water.

3. Establish a vision and strategy

- One of the strategies that the owner should consider implementing is to hire the right people that has the right skills to perform the assigned tasks. Since eco-tourism is a new thing in Brunei, the employees need to have a very clear understanding of what they are doing and why is it crucial to perform their tasks correctly. It will be an advantage if the employees have knowledge about the natural resources and can speak many languages. By implementing this, it will help to achieve SEV's vision.

4. Communicate the change vision

- The employees and the owner of SEV all have to work together as a team. Communication is important and it is the leader's job to let the employees know what are expected from them. This also goes to the employees. They need to express their lack of knowledge in certain things so that trainings can be provided.

5. Empower brand-based action

- According to the International Ecotourism Society, the definition of ecotourism is: "responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the well-being of local people." Therefore, SEV is an ecotourism spot where they still maintain the natural environment and minimizes the impact on the environment. The aim of creating SEV is to conserve the environment while bringing in economic benefits through tourism industry. Although SEV has created positive result in creating awareness and conserving the environment, the owner still finds it hard to promote SEV and to change individuals' mindset on ecotourism. In order to tackle this issue, actions should be taken on advertising what SEV has to offer to the public, both domestic and international.

6. Create short-term wins

- If the new strategies are successful in attracting more local and international visitors to come, it will benefit both SEV and the people as well. It will create job opportunities for people and SEV will get the exposure it deserves. It can also be the top of tourist attraction here in Brunei if the demand is high.

7. Consolidate gains and produce more change

- New strategies are to be implemented in this step. In order to get more visitors, SEV can offer special price according to holidays in Brunei. For example, since December is a school holiday, it is the time to offer special price for a family with children. It is also important to consistently maintain the environment as well as the cleanliness off the surrounding. When there are many visitors, things can be overwhelmed and get out of control. Therefore, it is important to ensure that the place is properly managed in order to conserve the natural environment.

8. Anchor new approaches in the culture

- Although the results cannot be seen immediately as it might takes months or years, it is very important to follow the strategies from what the leader has planned, discussed and assigned.

2.3 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project

Positive Model

In order to solve the issues faced by SCOT, the positive model of planned change will be used in analyzing this case. There are five phases under this model.

1. Initiate the Inquiry

- Funding is a major issue faced by SCOT. In order to carry out their programs effectively, they require funding through donations, sponsorships and government funding. There are also assumptions that NGOs like SCOT do not need funding because it is a voluntary work. However, this is just misunderstanding as most NGOs in Brunei need support in funding from the government in order to carry out project-based activities.

2. Inquire into Best Practices

- The Green Xchange project is the biggest event organized by SCOT and it is held annually. Basically, the objective of this project is to educate the public on the benefits of exchanging recyclable materials. In return, they will receive basic necessities such as rice. This is a good initiative made by SCOT. Instead of throwing out things that they do not know are recyclables into the landfill, they get to learn about things that they can actually recycle and get basic necessities in return. From this effort, Brunei can lessen the amount of trash being dumped at the landfills. According to JASTRe (2018), there are 189 thousand metric tons of waste are disposed each year. Through recycling, it can lessen the number of waste disposals.

3. Discover the Themes

- For this case, the theme will be a green transformation that is in line with Brunei's vision of 2035 that stated that the objective of seeing the growth of people with skilled that have the standard of international recognition, the growth of the living standard in order to create a more active and sustainable economic expansion. This initiative is also in line with the nation's 2035 vision that is to ensure that the environment of the country is not polluted

4. Envision a Preferred Future

- Through the Green Xchange project, the low-income earners are being educated on the opportunities of being entrepreneurship through effective waste management. In addition to that, this program is also helping the environment through the recycling activities being made. Although, it is quite difficult for SCOT to get monetary donations, it does not stop them to meet their mission in tackling with poverty issue in Brunei. The Green Xchange initiative is one of the biggest project and through improvising, has reached out to more people online.

5. Design and Deliver Ways to Create the Future

- If more people know what SCOT is and what do they do, people will not be hesitate to make donations and support the initiatives made by them. Not only they help the low-income people to earn side income, they also help to spread awareness of having environment without pollution.

3.0 Alternative Solutions

3.1 Possible solutions

The two models that used in analyzing the cases are the positive Model and the Kotter's Eight Steps Model. The most optimal to use in analyzing the cases are the positive model since it is mainly focuses on what the organization is doing right. It helps to understand what are the best that an organization can perform and from there, they create even improved results through their advantages. This concept is to transform its consistent performance with social sciences related growing movement known as the "positive organizational scholarship" on which, by focusing on the positive elements in organization gives tremendous results (Cummings & Worley, 2009). By analyzing using this model, there are possible solutions that can be used to solve the issues in the case studies.

The possible solutions for the BruTEL that wanted to "Go Paperless" in their billing system are to first understand the reasons why majority of the elderlies are not really supportive of this idea. By doing this, it would gain insight in to the linked between perceptions of the elderlies of digital advancement, technological assurance, and wellbeing (Alpass & Neville, 2003). Furthermore, it would also help the organization to communicate with the elderlies and encourage them to participate in the latest paperless trend and ensuring that fear or distrust in technology could be settle with training in digital skills (Lagana, 2008). According to Kenny & Milne (2014), the changes cannot be too drastic and should be begin with just one device such as the smart phone which can improve their skills if they are willing to learn. However, studies show that if the elderlies fail to address their fears in technology, it will not be successful in achieving the digital technologies. Hence, training programmes should be based on the barriers of technology before moving on to the benefits of using technology. In order to reach the customers regardless of their age, it is best to promote in different platforms such as social media, radio, television and radio.

In regards of analyzing the case of Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV), the Kotter's Eight Steps Model were used. This model focuses on leading change rather than managing it. It indicates the responsibility of the upper-level management in leading its organization through a change (Kreitner, 2007). The reason for choosing this model for this case is because it really suits with the story of the owner, Leslie Chiang, in trying to change the view of the people in eco-tourism. In order for ecotourism to be a success, one of the challenges include sustainability in balancing the components of economic, environment and social (TAT, 1997; WTO, 2002; Sangpikul, 2008). SEV needs to get continuous exposure by relevant ministries such as the Ministry of Primary Resources and Tourism and Radio Television Brunei (RTB).

Similar approach is done in Thailand whereby the government agencies of Thailand have actively promoted ecotourism among domestic and international tourists with the aim of contributing the benefits of ecotourism to the local communities as well as the country (TAT, 1997). Besides that, interesting activities should be added at SEV to get more people in. For example, bird watching, canoeing, snorkeling, scuba diving, education about the wildlife and nature or kayaking (Thailand Institute of Scientific and Technological Research, 1997). Despite all this, quick development without proper plan of the eco-tourism may lead to threats to the local tribes, degradation, and disturbance to the natural environment and conflict may arises over control of land.

Next is the possible solutions for Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT). Although SCOT has successfully helped many people in raising the awareness of waste management as well as decreasing the number of wastage going to the landfills, SCOT still finds it a challenge in terms of getting fund for the projects. This is common challenges for NGOs where they lack of resources and fund (Lewis, 2009). In order to tackle this issue, SCOT can collaborate with the relevant government and public agencies in terms of receiving sponsors for their cause. The easiest way to donate nowadays is through BIBD online application. However, SCOT has to be continuously active in carrying out their cause so that the public can get exposure on what they do. Therefore, they are more willing to donate rather than keeping it from the public.

4.0 Recommendations

4.1 Optimal solution

Based on the solutions that have been made for the three cases, the best optimal solution for all the three cases would be by collaborating with private and public agencies. The solution for the BruTEL's issue is to provide the training necessary for the elderlies in regards to the "Go Paperless" initiative. With the help from the private and government sectors, these senior citizens can learn and explore the advantages of using digital technology, from this, insights can be gained. This is supported by Thomas (2010) which stated that giving and accepting support through digital method improves a sense of connectiveness and wellbeing. In regards with motivation in using technology, the sense of self-efficacy among individual also allows the use of technology and their approval of the technology (Igbaria & Iivari, 1995).

This also applies to the issue of Sumbilicing Eco Village (SEV). If it is being well developed with the collaborations of the government and public sectors, it can be promoted as a center of interest or as a tourism product specialty appealing to visitors coming from both local and international (TAT, 1997; Patterson; 2002; Sang pikul, 2008). Out of all ecotourism stakeholders in Thailand, ecotourism that focus on business sector such as tour guides and accommodation is one of the important elements that contribute to the industry's success. This statement proves that if SEV is being managed properly with the help of relevant agencies, the tourism in Brunei can be expands and therefore give more diversity to the nation. The two key factors in offering quality ecotourism experience are implementation and the practice of sustainability and ecotourism principles (Wood, 2002; Donohoe & Needham, 2008).

Last but not least, the optimal solution can also be applied for the funding issue of SCOT in order for them to be able to create more projects. By having both private and public sectors to participate in raising the issues of poverty would create an impact to the nation. According to Bromideh (2011), relationship with government organizations and private sectors are the most important issues at national level.

5.0 Conclusion

To conclude, all the three cases are managed to be analyzed with the help of implementing conceptual models, theories and literature review of scholars that have done similar study outside of the country and in context of Brunei. The major findings in this report is that the importance of acknowledging what private and public sectors have got to offer. It is also vital to get them involved in handling issues in an organization because they have such a big impact in the country.

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